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Blumgart anastomosis versus invaginating pancreato-gastrostomy for reconstruction after Pancreatoduodenectomy: a randomized controlled trial.

--Manuscript Draft--

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If your submission contains figures, are any of them in color?	Yes, my submission has colored figures.
Are you and your coauthors willing to pay for color printing? as follow-up to "If your submission contains figures, are any of them in color?"	Yes, we will pay for color printing.
Do you or any of your coauthors have any potential conflicts of interest you need to declare?	The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest.
Was this submission funded by an outside agency (e.g., business, government agency, etc.)	Yes, we received funding.
How was your work supported? as follow-up to "Was this submission funded by an outside agency (e.g., business, government agency, etc.)"	This study was supported by a grant from Spain's Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through the Carlos III Health Institute (PI19/00250).
Does your study describe a Randomized Controlled Trial?	yes
SC 1. Does the Methods section contain a description of the Trial Design? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to explain how the Trial Design was done, and where this is found in the manuscript.	Trial design is described in the initial paragraph of the methods section. This was a single blinded multicenter two-arm 1:1 randomized controlled trial conducted at 13 tertiary Spanish hospitals. The trial was performed in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (14) and the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) guidelines. The CONSORT flow diagram is reported in Figure 1. The study protocol was approved by the Ethical committee of the promotor and reviewed by all the participating hospitals. The trial was registered in ClinicalTrials.gov with registration number NCT04462354. Data were collected by collaborating centers in an

	<p>anonymized on-line database designed by the promotor. Data collection was externally monitored by the Clinical Trial and Clinical Investigation Unit of the Biomedical Research Center INCLIVA, part of the Spanish Clinical Research Network (www.scren.eu).</p>
<p>SC 2. Does the Methods section describe the participants in the study? Eligibility criteria for participants and when applicable, eligibility criteria for centers (e.g., center volume, center resources, facilities, etc.) and surgeons (e.g., surgeons volume, specific training before trial initiation, etc.) should be included. Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe the participants and the selection procedure for them, and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	<p>Participants and centers selection is described in the Patients and Quality assessment sections of the Methods. Patients were eligible if they were >18 years old and presented a pancreatic or periampullary neoplasm which was considered susceptible of PD at local multidisciplinary meeting. Patients were excluded from the study if they presented pancreatic diseases other than periampullary neoplasm (i.e.: traumatism, pancreatitis, multi-visceral resection requiring PD), if pancreatic resection other than PD was performed (i.e.: central pancreatectomy), if none of the two anastomoses were employed due to technical difficulties, if PD was not performed for oncological reasons (i.e.: presence of metastases, etc), and if R2 resection was performed. The standardization of the surgical technique was ensured by the following steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Only centers with adequate surgical volume (17) and experience in both anastomotic techniques could participate in the trial. -All centers participated in an initial meeting where details of the two surgical techniques were discussed, and controversies debated and resolved by majority consensus. -Both anastomotic techniques were described in the study protocol and in step-by-step video guides delivered to participating surgeons.
<p>SC 3A. Does the Methods section include a description of the different components of the interventions (procedure, preoperative care (analgesics, antibiotics, etc.), anesthesia management, any devices or equipment used, postoperative care) and, when applicable, a description of the procedure for tailoring the interventions to individual participants? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe interventions and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	<p>Detailed surgical techniques and clinical follow up description are provided in The surgical techniques and follow up sections of the Methods.</p>
<p>SC 3B. Are details of whether and how the interventions were standardized (e.g., such as training, supervision of surgeons) included? Is there a description of the procedure for tailoring the interventions to individual participants? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe interventions and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	<p>The standardization of the procedure is detailed in the Quality assessment of surgical procedures section</p>
<p>SC 3C. Are details of whether and how adherence of surgeons with the protocol was assessed (e.g., review of case report</p>	<p>Interim analysis was performed after 100 patients were recruited. Complications were compared and adherence to the protocol assessed. Described in the Sample size section</p>

<p>forms, any other quality control procedure) or enhanced (e.g., refresh training of care providers) included in the interventions? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe surgeon adherence to the protocols and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	
<p>SC 4. Have pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures been completely defined, including how and when they were assessed? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe outcome measures and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	<p>Primary and secondary outcomes are specified in the outcomes section.</p>
<p>SC 5. Have you described the method used to generate the random allocation sequence? The mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned, as well as when were patients randomized (i.e., report the time point of allocation pre, intra, postoperative) should be included. Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe the randomization methods and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	<p>Described in the randomization section. Patients' allocation to BA or PG group was randomized using a computer-generated randomization sequence provided by the promotor, with 1:1 allocation and stratified by research site. Every research site received closed and sequentially numerated envelopes containing the allocation for each patient, which were opened following PD and before the reconstruction. Enrolment of patients was performed by the operating surgeon of each participating center. Patients were blind to the anastomosis performed.</p>
<p>SC 6. If blinding was done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe any blinding procedures used for this study and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	<p>Patients were blind. Single blinded.</p>
<p>SC 7. Have the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome for each group been described in the Results section? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe the treatment and outcome analysis of participants involved in this study and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	<p>Results are presented both Intention to threat and per protocol</p>
<p>SC 8. Does the Results section include a</p>	<p>Primary and secondary outcomes are described in Results and Table 1 and 2.</p>

<p>description of the results for each primary and secondary outcome, and the estimated effect size and its precision? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe the primary and secondary outcomes and where these are found in the manuscript.</p>	
<p>SC 9. Have all important harms or unintended effects in each group been described in the Results section? Please provide a detailed explanation (at least a few sentences) to describe harms or unintended effects reported in this study and where this is found in the manuscript.</p>	<p>Postoperative complications are one of the outcomes of the study and are described in Results.</p>
<p>SC 10. Has the trial registration number and name of trial registry been included? Please list the registration number and registry.</p>	<p>The trial was registered in ClinicalTrials.gov with registration number NCT04462354.</p>
<p>Have all coauthors viewed and approved of this version manuscript?</p>	<p>Yes - All coauthors have seen & approved</p>
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INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW

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To,

The Editor

Annals of Surgery

Dear Sir/Madam,

We are submitting the manuscript titled: "Blumgart anastomosis versus invaginating pancreato-gastrostomy for reconstruction after Pancreatoduodenectomy: a randomized controlled trial." under the ESA randomized controlled trial category for consideration towards publication in your esteemed journal. This article will not be sent to another journal until a decision is made concerning publication by Annals of Surgery. I accept to undertake full responsibility for authorship during the submission and review stages of the manuscript. The manuscript has been seen and approved by all authors.

Thanking you in anticipation,

Yours Sincerely,

Dimitri Dorcaratto MD., Ph.D.

Response to the reviewers

All corrections in the main manuscript, figures and tables have been highlighted in bold red.

REVIEWER 1

- This study is a welcome addition to the literature on pancreatic anastomosis techniques after pancreatoduodenectomy (PD). While meta-analyses suggest no difference in postoperative pancreatic fistula (POPF) rates between Blumgart anastomosis (BA) and invaginating pancreatogastrostomy (PG), this randomized controlled trial provides high-level evidence to support this conclusion.

We would like to warmly thank the reviewer for his comment on our work.

- The abstract mentions 16 university hospitals, but the methods section specifies 13 tertiary Spanish hospitals.

Thank you very much for noticing this mistake. 13 hospitals participated in the study. The error has been corrected in the abstract.

- while the study found no difference in overall POPF rates, it might be worthwhile to conduct subgroup analyses to explore potential differences in specific patient populations, such as those with soft pancreatic consistency or small pancreatic ducts.

This is an interesting point raised by the reviewer. Based on this comment we performed a sub-analysis of POPF rates in soft pancreatic texture and small Wirsung diameter patients (<3mm). No differences in POPF and B-C POPF rates were found between BA and PG groups in both subgroups analysis. The manuscript has been modified accordingly both in the Method, Results and Discussion sections as follow:

Method (Statistical analysis): Categorical variables were reported as frequencies and percentages and compared using the χ^2 test. Subgroup analysis comparing POPF and B-C POPF rates between

BA and PG in patients with soft pancreatic texture and narrow Wirsung (<3mm) was performed.

Results: POPF and B-C POPF rates were similar between BA and PG when compared in high risk patients (POPF rates: 61.1% vs 52.2%, $p=0.37$ and B-C POPF rates: 40.7% vs 32.6%, $p=0.4$ respectively in BA and PG group in soft pancreas patients; POPF rates 47.5% vs 45.8%, $p=0.84$ and B-C POPF rates 34.4% and 33.9%, $p=0.95$ respectively in BA and PG group in narrow Wirsung patients).

Discussion: Furthermore, no differences in POPF rates were observed when comparing high risk patients' subgroups.

- The power calculation described in the manuscript contains a typographical error, referring to '10% in the AB group' instead of 'BA group.'

Thank you very much. The typo has been corrected in the manuscript.

- Additionally, the assumed POPF rates for BA (10%) and PG (25%) differ substantially from the observed rates (BA: 40.5%, PG: 33.9%), which could significantly affect the study's power calculation. The authors need to discuss how these discrepancies might impact the study's statistical power and conclusions.

We thank the reviewer for this important observation. Although the sample size was calculated based on expected POPF rates supported by previously published literature, we agree that the actual POPF rates observed in our RCT are higher. These results may have significant implications for sample size calculations in future RCTs. If we recalculate the study's sample size using the same method (GRANMO) but with the observed POPF rates, we would have needed a total of 2,030 patients enrolled in the study (1,015 per arm). As the reviewer certainly knows, these numbers are nearly impossible to achieve in a surgical RCT. However, we fully agree with the reviewer that the study's power may be affected by the discrepancy between expected and observed POPF rates. Therefore, we have addressed this issue in the following paragraph, which has been added to the Discussion section of the manuscript:

POPF rates were higher than expected in both study arms. The discrepancy between expected and observed POPF might have impacted the power of the current study.

- the authors need to clarify if the study design was intended as a noninferiority trial, as implied in the introduction. If so, detailing the noninferiority margin (e.g., a one-directional difference of 5%) and its justification would be critical for properly evaluating the results.

Thank you for the comment. We are sorry for the misunderstanding. The trial was not meant to be a non-inferiority study. We thought that was clear, given the different POPF rates used in the sample size calculations. We understand that the reader could be confused by the Introduction of the manuscript, therefore, based on the reviewer comment, we modified the first paragraph of the Method section as follows:

This was a single blinded superiority multicenter two-arm 1:1 randomized controlled trial conducted at 13 tertiary Spanish hospitals.

- Figure 1 representing the CONSORT diagram is problematic, hinting at flaws in the analysis. The numbers in the PG allocation arm are inconsistent. The diagram indicates that 106 patients were allocated to PG, with 13 not receiving PG. However, with the 4 excluded patients, 17 did not receive PG.

Thank you for the observation. Figure 1 has been corrected accordingly.

- Explanations for exclusions, categorized as "Other reasons (n=7)," should be given.

Thank you for pointing this out. Of the 7 excluded patients, 4 decided to undergo the procedure at a private center different from the original, one underwent the procedure via laparoscopy, and 2 declined to participate in the study. The CONSORT flowchart has been modified according to your suggestion.

- the diagram reports no patients lost to follow-up, conflicting with the 10 Clavien-Dindo V mortalities reported. Clarifying whether the analysis accounted for the competing risk of death versus the development of POPF is important.

The reviewer is right: we should clarify that all patients were followed until the end of the study or death, with no loss to follow-up. To address this, we have added the following statement to the follow-up section in the Methods, and Figure 1 has been modified accordingly.

Patients were evaluated before surgery, on the day of surgery, daily during hospitalization, and at 1, 3, and 9 months postoperatively. Follow-up was stopped at 9 months after surgery, upon patient death, or upon voluntary withdrawal from the study.

- The manuscript lacks detail on whether the postoperative care team (e.g., residents, nurses) was blinded to the surgical techniques used (BA vs. PG), which is critical for avoiding bias in postoperative management and outcome assessment. It is also unclear whether there were any differences in postoperative care protocols, such as the timing of diet advancement, between the two cohorts. Please clarify.

Thank you for your comment. The strict word count limit for this publication forced us to omit some methodological details. Blinding of care providers was not planned, as most were present during surgery (surgeons and residents), and the on-call team needed full awareness of the operative technique in case of postoperative complications. We agree that you highlighted important details that should be included in the methodology section, and we have modified the Follow-up section accordingly, as follows:

Only patients were blinded to the surgical technique. They were evaluated before surgery, on the day of surgery, daily during hospitalization, and at 1, 3, and 9 months postoperatively. Follow-up was stopped at 9 months after surgery, upon patient death, or upon voluntary withdrawal from the study. No differences in postoperative care and follow-up protocols were planned between groups.

- Could the authors clarify if the surgeries at each center were performed by a single surgeon or by multiple surgeons?

Additionally, while the multicenter nature of the study is acknowledged as a potential limitation, further detail on the varying levels of expertise among centers and surgeons would be beneficial. This variability could influence the outcomes.

This important point raised by the reviewer was one of our main concerns during the trial design. For this reason, in the initial meeting, all surgeons from each collaborating center were required to declare their familiarity with both surgical techniques. Furthermore, explanatory videos of the anastomotic technique were reviewed, and any controversies were debated and resolved by majority consensus. However, no minimum number of previously performed procedures was established. We acknowledge that this could have influenced the study outcomes. Therefore, based on your comment, we have discussed this potential limitation as follows:

this was a multicenter study involving 13 Spanish hospitals, each performing fewer than 60 cases per year. All participating surgeons declared familiarity with both techniques, and this trial reflects real-world clinical practice in a European country. This is further supported by the rates of severe postoperative complications and mortality, which align with published international standards. However, the varying levels of experience in performing both techniques may have influenced the study outcomes.

The median of participating surgeons for every centre was 3 (1-6).

- A subgroup analysis comparing the outcomes of PG and BA within the same center would also be valuable. Such analysis would provide deeper insight into how surgical expertise may impact the effectiveness of each technique.

Thank you for your interesting suggestion. Based on it, we performed a subgroup analysis of POPF and BC-POPF within the same center to gain deeper insight into each center's experience with both techniques. No differences in POPF and BC-POPF between techniques were observed in the sub-analysis. We understand that this subgroup analysis was conducted as an internal mechanism to 'provide deeper insight into how surgical expertise may impact the effectiveness of

each technique' and that it is underpowered and performed post hoc. Therefore, we believe it is not necessary to include the results in the manuscript, especially given the limited word count. However, we are happy to consider any suggestions from the Editor.

- The manuscript should elaborate on any potential differences in the management of postoperative pancreatic fistula (POPF) and other complications between the Blumgart anastomosis (BA) and invaginating pancreato-gastrostomy (PG) groups. Specifically, it would be valuable to discuss whether the anatomical considerations of PG, which might allow easier access for endoscopic interventions, influenced the treatment strategies for managing complications. Additionally, in supplementary Table 1, the variable 'percutaneous or endoscopic procedure' should be detailed separately for each group to provide a clearer understanding of the interventional approaches taken.

We appreciate your insightful comment on this point. Based on it, we conducted a new comparison between BA and PG, distinguishing between endoscopic, angiographic, and percutaneous techniques for managing postoperative complications. No differences were found.

In response to your comment, we have modified Supplementary Table 1 and the Discussion as follows:

The management of postoperative complications was also similar between groups, without significant differences in the rates of therapeutic endoscopy, angiography and percutaneous procedures.

Supplementary table 1 has been modified according to the reviewer suggestion.

- Although it is acknowledged that oncological outcomes are not the primary focus of this trial, understanding the impact of POPF on the administration of adjuvant therapy is clinically significant. Given that POPF can potentially delay or prevent the initiation of adjuvant chemotherapy, it would be valuable for the authors to report on the proportion of patients in each cohort who were able to receive adjuvant therapy. This data would provide deeper insight into the practical implications of choosing one anastomotic technique over another. The authors are encouraged to include this

analysis to highlight the real-world consequences of POPF on postoperative cancer care.

Once again, we agree with the reviewer's comment. Therefore, we asked participating centers to provide postoperative chemotherapy data for the included patients. We compared postoperative chemotherapy administration rates and the completeness of perioperative chemotherapy between BA and PG, finding no significant differences in the intention-to-treat comparison. However, it is interesting to note that the per-protocol comparison of perioperative treatment completeness was nearly significant (65% for BA vs. 49% for PG, $p = 0.058$; Supplementary Table 6). Based on your observation, we have revised the manuscript and updated the tables as follows:

Method. Outcomes: adjuvant therapy rates and completeness of perioperative chemotherapy.

Supplementary Table 1: Postoperative chemotherapy rates (56% for BA versus 54% for PG). Completeness of perioperative chemotherapy (63% for BA VS 54% for PG).

Supplementary Table 6 and Results: However, BA patients completed the expected cycles of perioperative chemotherapy more often than PG patients (65.6% vs 49.2% respectively, $P=0.058$).

Discussion: Oncological outcomes are not reported in this trial. We believe that cancer-related survival and recurrence rates are influenced by several factors beyond the scope of an RCT evaluating an anastomotic technique. However, preoperative and postoperative chemotherapy administration rates were compared between groups, with no significant differences observed. Interestingly, in the per-protocol analysis, BA patients appear to complete perioperative treatment more frequently.

- While the study found no significant differences between BA and PG in the overall population for POPF, exploring subgroup differences, especially among high-risk patients with soft pancreatic consistency and small duct diameter, would be beneficial. Even though the study may not be powered for subgroup analyses, these insights could guide clinical decision-making in specific scenarios.

This is an interesting concern that was previously raised by the reviewer. Based on it, we conducted a subgroup

comparison in patients with soft pancreatic parenchyma and a small Wirsung duct. No differences were found. Please refer to the comment above and the modified manuscript.

- The fact that 13 patients were switched from PG to BA suggests limitations with PG in certain cases. This should be discussed more explicitly in the manuscript, providing practical recommendations for clinicians on when one technique might be preferred over the other.

We agree with the reviewer. This is one of the most interesting findings of the study. We did not discuss it further due to word count limitations and because, since the trial was negative on the primary outcome, we did not want to give the impression of being ‘biased’ toward one technique. However, we completely agree that in certain cases, BA could be easier to perform than PG. Therefore, we have modified the Discussion according to your comment as follows:

Surgeons had to change the anastomosis from PG to BA due to intraoperative technical difficulties in 13 out of 112 patients (12.7%). In almost all cases, the reason for the change was difficulty in mobilizing the pancreatic stump for proper intragastric invagination. This could be due to either chronic pancreatitis or a fatty and friable parenchyma.

None of the patients allocated to BA had to be converted to the PG group, even in cases with a small Wirsung diameter or soft pancreatic parenchyma. These findings suggest that pancreatic surgeons should be familiar with both techniques to manage unexpected intraoperative difficulties.

In particular, for patients who have experienced preoperative pancreatitis or are expected to have inflammatory changes in the surgical field, surgeons may prefer the BA technique to avoid extensive dissection of the pancreatic stump.

- The authors should clarify the number of participating centers. The abstract and discussion mention 16 centers, while the methods section lists 13. This discrepancy needs to be addressed.

We are sorry for the mistake. It has been addressed in the text.

- The manuscript should define what is considered 'adequate surgical volume' and 'expertise in both anastomotic techniques' as part of the centre selection criteria.

Thank you for this observation. To define 'adequate surgical volume,' we based our criteria on a previous publication from our group (Moya-Herraiz AA, Dorcaratto D, Martin-Perez E, et al. Non-arbitrary minimum threshold of yearly performed pancreatoduodenectomies: National multicentric study. *Surgery*. 2021;170(3):910-6.). Based on your comment, we have modified the 'Quality Assessment of Surgical Procedures' section as follows:

The standardization of the surgical technique was ensured by the following steps:

- *Only centers with adequate surgical volume (>30 pancreatic resections/year) (17) could participate in the trial.*
- *Participating surgeons should declare to be familiarized with both anastomotic techniques.*
- *All centers participated in an initial meeting where details of the two surgical techniques were discussed, and controversies debated and resolved by majority consensus.*
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- *The participating centers were requested to submit videos to the coordinating center demonstrating both surgical techniques.*

- The manuscript appears to lack the table comparing postoperative outcomes in the per-protocol analysis among the supplementary tables. Please provide this table to ensure the comprehensiveness of the data reporting.

Thank you for noticing. This was an editing mistake. We have now added the full per-protocol analysis to the supplementary material.

REVIEWER 2

- It's a prospective randomized study, clear and well written. The methodology was robust.

We appreciate the kind words of the reviewer.

- In order to better classify patients, why did the authors not use a pancreatic fistula risk score (several have been published in the literature)?

This is a very interesting point raised by the reviewer. We included all major POPF risk factors in the analysis but did not combine them into a single risk score. However, we agree with the reviewer that incorporating a risk score could be valuable. We decided to use the modified Fistula Risk Score (FRS) published by the Dutch Pancreatic Cancer Group (Mungroop et al., *Annals of Surgery*, 269(5):937-943, May 2019). No differences in FRS were observed between groups. The main manuscript and tables have been updated accordingly based on your comment.

Method. Outcomes section. Fistula Risk Score has been added. Tables 1 and Supplementary 5 have been modified accordingly.

- 100 patients have a soft pancreas. In the literature, there are several randomized trials that have demonstrated the benefits of an externalized stent, especially in patients with a soft pancreas. How can we justify not using this technique? On the contrary, no benefit has been demonstrated by a prospective randomized trial of an internal stent.

We appreciate the reviewer's comment. It is true that external stents have been suggested as a potential protective factor against POPF, particularly in high-risk patients. Several RCTs and meta-analyses support this. However, in clinical practice, the use of external stents depends on the personal preference of each surgeon. Standardizing their use across all 13 participating hospitals would have been extremely challenging. Additionally, we would have needed to stratify patients based on external stent use to avoid bias, which would have led to an unmanageable increase in sample size.

We acknowledge that this decision is debatable and should be highlighted in the manuscript's Discussion. Therefore, we have modified the Discussion as follows:

The current trial has some limitations that should be discussed. Firstly, as commented before, this was a multicentric study including 13 Spanish hospitals, all of them operating less than 60 cases per year. However, all participating surgeons declared to be familiarized with both techniques and this trial represents the real-life results of a European country daily clinical activity. This is confirmed by the rates of severe postoperative complications and mortality, which satisfy published international standards. POPF rates were higher than expected in both study arms. The discrepancy between expected and observed POPF might have impact the power of the current study. The multicentric nature of the study also influenced the decision not to use external pancreatic stents in high-risk patients due to the difficulties in standardizing this intervention across the 13 participating centers.

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Methods:

A multicenter, randomized, controlled trial was conducted in 13 University Hospitals. Eligible patients were those presenting a pancreatic or periampullary neoplasm undergoing PD. Assignment to each group (BA or PG) was randomized by blocks and stratified by centers. The primary endpoint was the rate of POPF with special assessment of clinically relevant (B-C) POPF; secondary endpoints were postoperative complications, factors related to POPF and quality of life (QoL).

Results:

Two hundred and sixteen patients were randomized. POPF and B-C POPF were 44%-28% in BA group and 34%- 23% in PG group ($p=0.39$ and $p=0.74$, respectively). Overall complications, severe complications and mortality rates were 76%, 24%, 3.7% respectively, in the BA group, and 73%, 32%, 5.9%, in the PG group, with no significant differences. Soft pancreatic consistency, small preoperative CT Wirsung diameter, patient age, and 1st postoperative drain amylase concentration were independently associated with B-C POPF. QoL functional scales favoured the PG anastomosis at 9-months.

Conclusions:

BA and PG showed no differences in POPF and postoperative outcomes; B-C POPF can be predicted based on several pre-intra and early postoperative parameters; QoL favoured PG anastomosis at 9 months.

Blumgart anastomosis versus invaginating pancreato-gastrostomy for reconstruction after Pancreatoduodenectomy: a randomized controlled trial.

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Luis Sabater-Ortí; D. Dorcaratto: integrity of the data and the accuracy of the data analysis.

Dimitri Dorcaratto, Marina Garcés-Albir, Luis Sabater-Ortí: concept and design.

Dimitri Dorcaratto, Marina Garcés-Albir, Sara Palomares-Casasús: drafting of the manuscript.

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Javier Padillo-Ruiz, Luis Sabater-Ortí: supervision.

The authors report no conflicts of interest.

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Conclusions:

BA and PG showed no differences in POPF and postoperative outcomes; B-C POPF can be predicted based on several pre-intra and early postoperative parameters; QoL favoured PG anastomosis at 9 months.

INTRODUCTION

Pancreatoduodenectomy (PD), together with perioperative chemotherapy, represents the main pillar for the treatment of tumors involving the pancreatoduodenal area. Despite the advances in perioperative care, post-PD morbidity rates are still as high as 65.3% (1). Of these complications, postoperative pancreatic fistula (POPF) is known as one of the most worrisome. With POPF rates remaining above 25% (2) and the proved detrimental effect of complications on oncological results (3), the continuous efforts to improve surgical results are justified. Until now, most of the trials comparing pancreato-enteric anastomotic techniques have failed in the task of finding the “best” anastomosis (4, 5). It has been proven that some patient-related factors such as gender, body mass index, pancreatic consistency, Wirsung duct diameter or benign disease are the most important determinants of POPF risk (6). However, none of these factors are modifiable. Therefore, an exquisite anastomotic technique is currently the only instrument that surgeons hold in their hands to diminish POPF rates.

Invaginating pancreato-gastrostomy (PG) is recognised as a secure anastomotic technique and is currently widely used after PD (7-9). However, postoperative intraluminal hemorrhage and the sometimes-difficult dissection of pancreatic stump for a tensionless invagination are regarded as possible limitations of PG anastomosis (10). Dr Leslie H. Blumgart proposed in 2000 an anastomotic technique, involving duct-to-mucosa pancreato-jejunosomy (PJ) and a full-thickness jejunal wrap around the pancreatic stump (11). The Blumgart Anastomosis (BA) has proven to be secure (12) and comparable to other duct-to-mucosa PJ (2, 13).

The hypothesis of this study was whether BA could decrease POPF rates when compared to PG in a randomized controlled trial (RCT).

METHODS

This was a single blinded **superiority** multicenter two-arm 1:1 randomized controlled trial conducted at 13 tertiary Spanish hospitals. The trial was performed in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (14) and the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) guidelines. The CONSORT flow diagram is reported in Figure 1. The study protocol was approved by the Ethical committee of the promotor and reviewed by all the participating hospitals. The trial was registered in ClinicalTrials.gov with registration number NCT04462354. Data were collected by collaborating centers in an anonymized on-line database designed by the promotor. Data collection was externally monitored by the Clinical Trial and Clinical Investigation Unit of the Biomedical

Research Center INCLIVA, part of the Spanish Clinical Research Network (www.scren.eu).

Patients

Patients were eligible if they were >18 years old and presented a pancreatic or periampullary neoplasm which was considered susceptible of PD at local multidisciplinary meeting. Patients were excluded from the study if they presented pancreatic diseases other than periampullary neoplasm (i.e.: traumatism, pancreatitis, multi-visceral resection requiring PD), if pancreatic resection other than PD was performed (i.e.: central pancreatectomy), if none of the two anastomoses were employed due to technical difficulties, if PD was not performed for oncological reasons (i.e.: presence of metastases, etc), and if R2 resection was performed.

Randomization and Blinding

Patients' allocation to BA or PG group was randomized using a computer-generated randomization sequence provided by the promotor, with 1:1 allocation and stratified by research site. Every research site received closed and sequentially numerated envelopes containing the allocation for each patient, which were opened following PD and before the reconstruction. Enrolment of patients was performed by the operating surgeon of each participating center. Patients were blind to the anastomosis performed.

Surgical Techniques

PD with or without pylorus preservation was performed depending on clinical requirements. After pancreatic resection, pancreato-digestive anastomosis was carried out either using BA or PG. In the BA group a jejunal loop was brought to the pancreas. BA was performed as described by Grobmyer et al (15), figure 2. A plastic stent was inserted in the duct-to-mucosa anastomosis. The same jejunal loop used for the BA was then anastomosed to the bile duct and the stomach. Jejuno-jejunostomy (Brown anastomosis) was optional. Invaginating PG was performed as described in a previous RCT by Figueras et al (7), figure 2. A single jejunal loop was used for bilio-enteric and gastro-jejunal anastomosis. One surgical non aspirative drain was placed near the pancreato-enteric anastomosis. Pancreato-enteric abdominal drain amylase concentration was analyzed on days 1 and 3 postoperative (p.o.) and previously published protocol was used for drains management (16). Blood analyses including C reactive protein, procalcitonin, blood count and renal function were performed on day 1 and 3 p.o. and when clinically indicated.

Quality assessment of surgical procedures

The standardization of the surgical technique was ensured by the following steps:

- **Only centers with adequate surgical volume (>30 pancreatic resection/year) (17) could participate in the trial.**
- **Participating surgeons should declare to be familiarized with both anastomotic techniques.**
- All centers participated in an initial meeting where details of the two surgical techniques were discussed, and controversies debated and resolved by majority consensus.
- Both anastomotic techniques were described in the study protocol and in step-by-step video guides delivered to participating surgeons.
- **The participating centers were requested to submit videos to the coordinating center demonstrating both surgical techniques.**

Follow up

Only patients were blinded to the surgical technique. They were evaluated before surgery, on the day of surgery, daily during hospitalization, and at 1, 3, and 9 months postoperatively. Follow-up was stopped at 9 months after surgery, upon patient death, or upon voluntary withdrawal from the study. No differences in postoperative care and follow-up protocols were planned between groups.

Outcomes

The primary end point of the study was to evaluate the incidence of POPF and clinically relevant POPF as defined by the International Study Group of Pancreatic Surgery (ISGPF) (18). Secondary endpoints were the following: complications and severe complications rates; the impact of independent variables on POPF, grade B and C POPF and severe p.o. complication rates (Clavien-Dindo >2) (18), and the quality of life (QoL) 3 months and 9 months after surgery.

Variables included in the study were age; gender; preoperative weight loss (calculated as usual weight-preoperative weight/usual weight); body mass index; preoperative diabetes, pancreatitis and jaundice; preoperative biliary drain; neoadjuvant therapy; American Society of Anaesthesiology (ASA) classification (19); main pancreatic duct diameter (both preoperatively on CT scan and intraoperatively); portal phase enhanced pancreatic parenchyma attenuation on preoperative CT scan as described previously (20); intraoperative pancreatic consistency (soft/hard); **Fistula Risk Score (21)**; anatomopathological study of the specimen; venous resection and reconstruction method; specific complications as defined and graded by ISGPF (delayed gastric empty, postoperative hemorrhage, bile leak) (22-24); complication during the first 90 days p.o. classified using the Clavien-Dindo (C-D) classification (25) and the Comprehensive Complication Index (CCI) (26); operation and anastomotic time; intraoperative blood transfusion; hospital stay and readmission rates; p.o. days 1 and 3 C reactive protein (CRP) and procalcitonin concentrations; p.o. days 1

and 3 drain amylase concentration; surgical drain removal timing; **adjuvant therapy rates and completeness of perioperative chemotherapy**; 3 and 9 months p.o. exocrine pancreatic insufficiency symptoms (diarrhea, fatty stool), pancreatic enzymes use and weight loss. Quality of Life was evaluated using the European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) QLQ-C30 and PAN-26 questionnaires (<https://qol.eortc.org/questionnaires/>).

Sample size

Sample size calculation was performed with the GRANMO freeware (27) based on previous publications reporting POPF rates both for BA and PG (2, 7-9, 13, 28, 29). POPF rates of 10% in the **BA** group and 25% in the PG group were assumed. With the significance threshold set at 5%, power at 80% and patients' loss at 10%, the sample size calculation indicated a study population of 216. Interim analysis was performed after recruiting 100 patients, comparing clinically significant POPF, complications and mortality rates between groups.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis was conducted on both intention-to-treat and per-protocol basis by the independent provider IDAL (Intelligent Data Analysis Laboratory) associated to the University of Valencia, Spain. Continuous variables were assessed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Since none of the continuous variables followed a normal distribution, they were summarized as medians with interquartile ranges and compared using the Mann-Whitney U test. Categorical variables were reported as frequencies and percentages and compared using the χ^2 test. **Subgroup analysis comparing POPF and B-C POPF rates between BA and PG in patients with soft pancreatic texture and narrow Wirsung (<3mm) was performed.**

To evaluate the impact of independent variables on POPF, clinically significant POPF, and severe postoperative complications, logistic regression analysis was employed. Variables with a P-value < 0.1 in the initial Mann-Whitney U test or χ^2 test were included in the logistic regression model. A backward selection process based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was then applied to refine the model by reducing the number of independent variables.

The impact on Quality of Life was assessed using a paired Friedman test for intra-group evolution (with a Durbin-Conover post-hoc analysis) and a Mann-Whitney test for inter-group differences between protocols.

All statistical tests were two-tailed, with a P-value < 0.05 considered indicative of statistical significance. Statistical analyses were performed using R software (version 4.3.2).

RESULTS

Two hundred and sixteen patients were randomized between June 2020 and June 2023. Four patients were excluded after randomization, leaving 110 patients in the BA group and 102 in the PG group (Figure 1).

The two groups were comparable regarding patient demographic and intraoperative characteristics, which are shown in Table 1, except for age. However, in 13 (12.7%) patients of the PG group, the operating surgeon had to perform Blumgart anastomosis due to intraoperative findings (mainly secondary to technical difficulties in the pancreatic stump dissection for invagination). All BA patients received the planned anastomosis ($p < 0.001$).

Postoperative POPF, B-C POPF, complication and severe complication rates were comparable between groups (Table 2). Other relevant postoperative results are summarized in Supplementary Table 1. **POPF and B-C POPF rates were similar between BA and PG when compared in high risk patients (POPF rates: 61.1% vs 52.2%, $p=0.37$ and B-C POPF rates: 40.7% vs 32.6%, $p=0.4$ respectively in BA and PG group in soft pancreas patients; POPF rates 47.5% vs 45.8%, $p=0.84$ and B-C POPF rates 34.4% and 33.9%, $p=0.95$ respectively in BA and PG group in narrow Wirsung patients).**

Predictors of the development of POPF; B-C POPF and severe p.o. complications are shown in Supplementary Table 2. Soft pancreatic consistency, preoperative CT small Wirsung diameter, prolonged anastomotic time and increased drain amylase concentration on day 1 p.o. were independent risk factors for POPF. Soft pancreatic consistency, small preoperative CT Wirsung diameter, increased patient age, and increased drain amylase concentration were independently associated with B-C POPF. Serum procalcitonin concentration on day 3 p.o. was the only factor associated with severe complications.

Overall, QoL was comparable between groups (supplementary Figure 1 and supplementary Table 3). Symptoms and functional scales showed differences in favour of the PG anastomosis at 9-months p.o. Intra-subject analysis, comparing the results within the same group (supplementary Table 4), showed no differences in QoL across the different time periods in the BA group. On the other hand, patients with PG anastomosis experienced a worsening 3 months after surgery in the symptoms and function areas, recovering baseline levels at 9 months p.o. Moreover, PG patients showed an improvement 9 months after surgery compared to baseline in the global health area and in QLQ-26.

Per protocol comparison of pre-, intra-, postoperative variables and QoL did not show any differences between groups in primary and secondary outcomes (Supplementary Tables 5 and 6). **However, BA patients completed the expected cycles of perioperative chemotherapy more often than PG patients (65.6% vs 49.2% respectively, $P=0.058$).**

DISCUSSION

The current study, representing the first RCT comparing BA with PG after PD, suggests that both anastomoses are feasible and safe. No differences in POPF, clinically relevant POPF and postoperative complication rates were found. Almost all main postoperative outcomes were within the benchmarks established on optimal, low-risk patients (1). However, clinically relevant POPF rates (24%) were slightly higher than the ones published by Hirono et al (7-10%) (13) and Halloran et al (11%) (2) and similar to the ones published by Cheng et al (19%) in a systematic review of 10 RCTs (4). This difference may be explained by the strict clinical follow-up employed in our trial and by the multicentric nature of the current study. **No differences in POPF rates were observed when comparing high risk patients subgroups.**

The study provides some important data on factors associated with POPF and postoperative complications. Firstly, reduced Wirsung diameter and decreased pancreatic parenchyma attenuation on preoperative CT scan were both associated with B-C POPF. These results confirm previous studies indicating that preoperative CT evaluation is useful to predict POPF (20, 30-32). However, the weak association between pancreatic attenuation and B-C POPF suggests the need to investigate new methods of preoperative evaluation of the pancreatic parenchyma, such as texture analysis (33). Another valuable finding was that increased procalcitonin concentration on POD 3 was associated with severe postoperative complications, as observed in retrospective studies (34). Smits et al previously outlined the importance of early detection of postoperative complications in order to decrease mortality (35). Finally, the model consisting of soft pancreatic consistency, small Wirsung diameter, increased patient age, and elevated POD 1 drain amylase concentration could predict the development of B-C POPF, helping to identify high-risk patients who will need extra postoperative vigilance. On the other hand, surgical drain amylase concentrations on days 1 and 3 p.o. were slightly higher in the BA group than in the PG group, but this finding had no clinical significance in the development of POPF or complications.

Concerns have been raised about the security of PG in terms of postoperative hemorrhage and possible technical difficulties in the dissection of fibrotic and inflamed pancreatic stumps (9, 36, 37). In the current trial, hemorrhage rates were 15% and 21% in the BA and PG group respectively, with no statistical difference. On the other hand, **surgeons had to change the anastomosis from PG to BA due to intraoperative technical difficulties in 13 out of 112 patients (12.7%). In almost all cases, the reason for the change was difficulty in mobilizing the pancreatic stump for proper intragastric invagination. This could be due to either chronic pancreatitis or a fatty and friable parenchyma.**

None of the patients allocated to BA had to be converted to the PG group, even in cases with a small Wirsung diameter or soft pancreatic

parenchyma. These findings suggest that pancreatic surgeons should be familiar with both techniques to manage unexpected intraoperative difficulties. In particular, for patients who have experienced preoperative pancreatitis or are expected to have inflammatory changes in the surgical field, surgeons may prefer the BA technique to avoid extensive dissection of the pancreatic stump. After allocating the 13 patients in the BA groups, there was no additional difference in postoperative outcomes in per protocol analysis. The management of postoperative complications was also similar between groups, without significant differences in the rates of therapeutic endoscopy, angiography and percutaneous procedures.

Patient reported quality of life was similar between the two groups both preoperatively and 3 months after surgery. Irrespective of the anastomotic technique employed, patients experienced a general worsening of QoL in 3 months p.o., with a trend towards amelioration in 9 months p.o. However, this worsening in the early p.o. period was more intense in the PG group. This finding could explain the greater recovery in functionality and symptoms 9 months p.o. in the PG group. These results confirm the findings showed by Halloran et al (2) and add valuable information by using the PAN-26 specific pancreatic questionnaire for the first time in a RCT on Blumgart anastomosis.

No differences in weight loss, use of pancreatic enzymes supplements and exocrine insufficiency symptoms were detected between the two groups 9 months after surgery. These findings suggest good functional results of BA and they are very important because, to our knowledge, this is the first time they have been reported in a RCT comparing Blumgart anastomosis to other techniques.

Oncological outcomes are not reported in this trial. We believe that cancer-related survival and recurrence rates are influenced by several factors beyond the scope of an RCT evaluating an anastomotic technique. However, preoperative and postoperative chemotherapy administration rates were compared between groups, with no significant differences observed. Interestingly, in the per-protocol analysis, BA patients appear to complete perioperative treatment more frequently.

The current trial has some limitations that should be discussed. Firstly, as commented before, **this was a multicenter study involving 13 Spanish hospitals, each performing fewer than 60 cases per year. All participating surgeons declared familiarity with both techniques, and this trial reflects real-world clinical practice in a European country. This is further supported by the rates of severe postoperative complications and mortality, which align with published international standards. However, the varying levels of experience in performing both techniques may have influenced the study outcomes. POPF rates were higher than expected in both study arms. The discrepancy between expected and observed POPF might have impacted the**

power of the current study. The multicentric nature of the study also influenced the decision not to use external pancreatic stents in high-risk patients due to the difficulties in standardizing this intervention across the 13 participating centers. Despite these limitations, the current study represents the first RCT comparing two widely diffused pancreatic anastomotic techniques. It provides solid data which can be used in future studies to continue progressing in the difficult path of finding a feasible and safe pancreato-enteric anastomosis.

In summary, the current RCT, suggests that both BA and PG are feasible and safe; preoperative CT evaluation of the pancreas is useful to predict POPF; procalcitonin can be used for early detection of severe postoperative complications and the model consisting in soft pancreatic consistency, small Wirsung diameter, increased patient age and elevated day 1 p.o. drain amylase concentration can adequately predict the development of B-C POPF.

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Figure legends.

Figure 1: Consort flow diagram for the trial.

Figure 2: Technical details of Blumgart (BA; 1) and pancreato-gastric (PG; 2) anastomoses. 1A: BA. Monofilament trans-pancreatic double needle sutures (usually 4 to 6) are passed through the pancreatic parenchyma, the posterior jejunal wall and back through the pancreatic gland. 1B: BA. Duct to mucosa pancreato-jejunostomy is performed usually using 6-8 monofilament separate sutures. 1C: BA. Before completing the duct to mucosa anastomosis, an internal silicone stent is passed from the main pancreatic duct to the bowel. 1D: BA. After completing the duct to mucosa anastomosis, trans-pancreatic sutures are knotted and passed through the anterior jejunal wall to invaginate the pancreatic stump. 2A: PG. Apposition of the posterior seromuscular wall of the stomach to the anterior capsule of the pancreas is performed with interrupted monofilament sutures. A small gastrotomy is made in the posterior gastric wall. 2B: PG. The pancreatic remnant is invaginated into the gastric lumen. 2C: PG. A running suture is performed between the gastric mucosa and the capsule of the invaginated pancreatic remnant. 2D: PG. The pancreatic posterior capsule and gastric seromuscular layer are joined with interrupted sutures.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics and Intraoperative Findings.

	Overall (N =212)	BA (N = 110)	PG (N =102)	P Value
Age, median (IQR) , years	69 (61-75)	66 (59-73)	70 (63-76)	0.02
Sex, N (%)				1.00
Male	105 (50)	55 (50)	50 (49)	
Female	107 (50)	55 (50)	52 (51)	
BMI, median (IQR)	25.48 (22.6-28.9)	24.74 (22.32-2)	26.17 (23.00-29.3)	0.13
Diabetes, N (%)	68 (32)	32 (29)	36 (35)	0.41
Pancreatitis, N (%)	16 (7.5)	7 (6.4)	9 (8.8)	0.68
Jaundice, N (%)	143 (67)	72 (65)	71 (70)	0.62
Preoperative biliary drainage, N (%)	117 (55)	58 (53)	59 (58)	0.54
Biliary drainage type, N (%)				0.76
None	95 (45)	52 (47)	43 (42)	
Endoscopic	107 (50%)	53 (48)	54 (53)	
Percutaneous	10 (4.7%)	5 (4.5)	5 (4.9)	
Pancreatitis post-drainage, N (%)	11 (5.2)	7 (6.4)	4 (3.9)	0.63
Preoperative chemotherapy, N (%)	38 (18)	21 (19)	17 (17)	0.78
Preoperative radiotherapy, N (%)	11 (5.2)	4 (3.6)	7 (6.9)	0.45
ASA score, N (%)				0.28
I-II	102 (48.1)	49 (48)	53 (52)	
III-IV	110 (51.9)	61 (55.5)	49 (44.5)	
Cardiopulmonary disease, N (%)	75 (35)	40 (36)	35 (34)	0.87
Percentage of preoperative weight loss, median (IQR)	0.04 (0.00-0.08)	0.04 (0.00-0.09)	0.03 (0.00-0.07)	0.14
Preoperative Wirsung diameter, median (IQR), mm	3 (2-6)	4 (2-6)	3 (2-6)	0.85
Pancreas' attenuation, median (IQR), HU	90 (75.75-110)	89.50 (77.50-106.75)	90.00 (75.25-110)	0.93
Pancreatic texture, N (%)				0.66
Hard	112 (53)	56 (51)	56 (55)	
Soft	100 (47)	54 (49)	46 (45)	
Wirsung diameter, median (IQR), mm	3 (2-5)	3 (2-5)	3 (2-5)	0.15
Fistula Risk Score, median (IQR)	25 (32)	23 (28)	29 (33)	0.18
Estimated intraoperative blood loss, median (IQR), mL	300(190-400)	300 (150-400)	300 (200-412.50)	0.64
Intraoperative transfusion, N (%)	22 (10)	14 (13)	8 (7.8)	0.35
Intraoperative complication, N (%)	6 (2.8)	3 (2.7)	3 (2.9)	1.00
Time of surgery, median (IQR), min	300 (245.25-360.00)	300 (248.50-359)	285 (246-360)	0.32
Time of reconstruction, median (IQR), min	35 (25-40)	35 (30-40)	35 (25-45)	0.75
Venous resection, N (%)	37 (17)	18 (16)	19 (19)	0.80
Type of venous reconstruction, N (%)				0.65
Venorrhaphy	11 (5.2)	4 (3.6)	7 (6.9)	
End-to-end anastomosis	20 (9.4)	10 (9.1)	10 (9.8)	
Graft	6 (2.8)	4 (3.6)	2 (2)	
Pylorus-preserving, N (%)	19 (9)	14 (13)	5 (4.9)	0.08
Pancreatic division method, N (%)				0.45
Cold scalpel	53 (25)	27 (25)	26 (25)	
Electric scalpel	126 (59)	65 (59)	61 (60)	
Ultrasound device	24 (11)	13 (12)	11 (11)	
Others	6 (2.8)	2 (1.8)	4 (3.9)	
Not specified	3 (1.4)	3 (2.7)	0 (0)	
Patients' crossover, N (%)	13 (6,13)	0 (0)	13 (13.7)	0.01

ASA: American Society of Anesthesiology; BMI: body mass index (calculated as weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared); PG: pancreaticogastrostomy; BA: Blumgart Anastomosis.

Table2. Main postoperative outcomes.

	Overall (N =212)	BA (N = 110)	PG (N =102)	P Value
Drain amylase concentration – POD 1, median (IQR), IU/L	412 (44-2068.7)	653.5 (46.75-2767.5)	290.50 (44-1120.5)	0.08
CRP - POD 1, median (IQR), mg/L	95 (70.7-132.3)	89 (68.75-120.6)	101 (73.6-136.5)	0.06
Procalcitonin -POD 1, median (IQR), ng/mL	5.00 (3-11)	5 (2-11)	5 (3-12)	0.35
Drain amylase concentration – POD 3, median (IQR), IU/L	124.50 (17.50-876.75)	216 (16.50-1672)	81 (19-665)	0.19
CRP - POD 3, median (IQR), mg/L	197.5 (128.4-264.5)	188.2 (116-259.2)	200.3 (139.7-269.5)	0.24
Procalcitonin - POD 3, median (IQR), ng/mL	3 (1-6)	3 (1-6)	3 (2-6)	0.49
Length of stay, median (IQR), days	13 (9-21)	12 (9-20)	13 (9-22)	0.56
Pancreatic fistula, N (%)	78 (37)	44 (40)	34 (33)	0.39
Fistula degree, N (%)				0.65
Grade A	27 (13)	16 (15)	11 (11)	
Grade B	40 (19)	23 (21)	17 (17)	
Grade C	11 (5.2)	5 (4.5)	6 (5.9)	
Fistula grade B-C, N (%)	51 (24)	28 (25)	23 (23)	0.74
Postoperative haemorrhage, N (%)	37 (17)	16 (15)	21 (21)	0.33
Time of haemorrhage, N (%)				0.36
Early	3 (1.4)	2 (1.8)	1 (1)	
Late	34 (16)	14 (13)	20 (20)	
Type of haemorrhage, N (%)				0.45
Endoluminal	16 (7.5)	6 (5.5)	10 (9.8)	
Extraluminal	20 (9.4)	10 (9.1)	10 (9.8)	
Non-specified	1 (0.5)	0 (0)	1 (1.0)	
Haemorrhage degree, N (%)				0.43
Grade A	13 (6.1)	6 (5.5)	7 (6.9)	
Grade B	8 (3.8)	2 (1.8)	6 (5.9)	
Grade C	16 (7.5)	8 (7.3)	8 (7.8)	
Delayed gastric emptying, N (%)	51 (24)	24 (22)	27 (26)	0.53
Type of delayed gastric emptying, N (%)				0.73
Grade A	23 (11)	11 (10)	12 (12)	
Grade B	19 (9.0)	9 (8.3)	10 (9.8)	
Grade C	8 (3.8)	3 (2.8)	5 (4.9)	
Biliary fistula, N (%)	17 (8.0)	10 (9.1)	7 (6.9)	0.73
Type of biliary fistula, N (%)				0.44
Grade A	5 (2.4)	4 (3.6)	1 (1.0)	
Grade B	11 (5.2)	5 (4.5)	6 (5.9)	
Grade C	1 (0.5)	1 (0.9)	0 (0)	
Reintervention, N (%)	24 (11)	11 (10)	13 (13)	0.68
Postoperative complication, N (%)	158 (75)	84 (76)	74 (73)	0.63
Clavien Dindo score \geq III, N (%)	59 (28)	26 (24)	33 (32)	0.21
Clavien Dindo 90 POD, N (%)				0.53
0	38 (18)	20 (18)	18 (18)	
I	23 (11)	13 (12)	10 (9.8)	
II	91 (43)	51 (47)	40 (39)	
IIIa	23 (11)	11 (10)	12 (12)	
IIIb	17 (8.1)	5 (4.6)	12 (12)	
IVa	5 (2.4)	2 (1.8)	3 (2.9)	
IVb	4 (1.9)	3 (2.8)	1 (1)	
V	10 (4.7)	4 (3.7)	6 (5.9)	

Abbreviations: BA, Blumgart anastomosis; CRP, C-reactive protein; EPI, exocrine pancreatic insufficiency; PG, pancreaticogastrostomy; POD, postoperative day; POM, postoperative month.

Figure 1

Figure 2

1

2

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Supplemental Data File

Supplementary Table 1 Posoperative outcomes
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Supplementary Table 2 Risk model.docx

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CONSORT 2010 checklist of information to include when reporting a randomised trial*

Section/Topic	Item No	Checklist item	Reported on page No
Title and abstract			
	1a	Identification as a randomised trial in the title	1
	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstracts)	4
Introduction			
Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	6
	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	6
Methods			
Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	6
	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	/
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	7
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	7
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	7
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	8
	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	/
Sample size	7a	How sample size was determined	9
	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	9
Randomisation:			
Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	7
	8b	Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	7
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	7
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	7
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those	6

		assessing outcomes) and how	
Statistical methods	11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	7
	12a	Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	9
	12b	Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses	9
Results			
Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	9-10
	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	9-10
Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	9-10
	14b	Why the trial ended or was stopped	
Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	T1
Numbers analysed	16	For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups	9-10 fig 1
Outcomes and estimation	17a	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)	9-10. Tab 2 supplementar y Tab 1
	17b	For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended	Tab 2
Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	
Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	/
Discussion			
Limitations	20	Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses	10-11
Generalisability	21	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	10-11
Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	10-11
Other information			
Registration	23	Registration number and name of trial registry	6
Protocol	24	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available	6
Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	2

*We strongly recommend reading this statement in conjunction with the CONSORT 2010 Explanation and Elaboration for important clarifications on all the items. If relevant, we also recommend reading CONSORT extensions for cluster randomised trials, non-inferiority and equivalence trials, non-pharmacological treatments, herbal interventions, and pragmatic trials. Additional extensions are forthcoming: for those and for up to date references relevant to this checklist, see www.consort-statement.org.

CONSORT 2010 Flow Diagram

